

AUTOMATED GUIDED VEHICLE

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ABSTRACT

High demands on manufacturers have left their shipping warehouses in havoc. Human error has a negative effect on safety, efficiency, and quality. These expenses are reduced with the introduction of an Automated Guided Vehicle, AGV. A driverless, intelligent forklift uses an optical path to quickly and safely traverse a warehouse. Its Capabilities are enhanced by the ability to send and receive tasks through RF data communication. The project designer was highly skilled in the 'C' and 'C++' language and had to make adjustment to his coding techniques to adjust for inadequacies in the compiler